

Enhancing AAC Devices with Generative AI for Natural and Expressive Speech Synthesis

Juliana Francis¹, Éva Székely¹, Joakim Gustafson¹

*¹ Division of Speech, Music, and Hearing, KTH Royal Institute of Technology,
Stockholm, Sweden*

jfrancis@kth.se, szekely@kth.se, jkgu@kth.se

Abstract

Introduction: The advancement of generative AI in speech synthesis holds transformative potential for Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) devices, aiming to enhance the speed and naturalness of speech for users. This project focuses on developing and integrating generative AI to create expressive, conversational speech synthesis, ultimately improving the social inclusion of individuals relying on AAC devices.

Objectives: The primary objective is to leverage generative AI to develop an AAC system that provides contextually appropriate and naturally sounding speech. Specific goals include:

- Enhancing speech prediction accuracy using contextual data from Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR).
- Implementing style-adaptive Text-to-Speech (TTS) that interpolates between reading and conversational styles.
- Evaluating the system's effectiveness in reducing the communication effort for AAC users.

Current Work: We have developed a research prototype named ConnecTone, which serves as a modular platform for rapid integration and testing of language generation and speech technology. ConnecTone incorporates:

- **Contextual Generative Text Prediction:** Using conversational context from ASR inputs, ConnecTone predicts desired speech and provides multiple speech options generated by a Large Language Model (LLM).
- **Style-Adaptive TTS:** This component supports interpolation between reading and spontaneous conversational styles, allowing users to adjust prosodic features such as speech rate and pitch.

Planned Work: The upcoming phases of the project will involve:

- **User Studies:** Conducting extensive user studies with AAC device users to gather feedback and refine the system.
- **Enhanced Context Integration and Prosodic Control:** Implement object detection and user control of prosody via gaze and facial expressions.
- **Integration and Testing:** Integrating ASR components for better contextual understanding and implementing user-specific customization features.

Expected Outcomes: The project aims to deliver an AAC system that significantly reduces the communication time and effort for users. By generating more natural and contextually appropriate speech, we anticipate that users will experience enhanced social interactions and greater inclusion in daily activities.

References

- Valencia, S., Cave, R., Kallarackal, K., Seaver, K., Terry, M., & Kane, S. (2023). "The less I type, the better": How AI Language Models can Enhance or Impede Communication for AAC Users. Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3581560>
- Székely, E., Wang, S., & Gustafson, J. (2023). *So-to-Speak: an exploratory platform for investigating the interplay between style and prosody in TTS*. <https://www.speech.kth.se/tts-demos/SoToSpeak/SoToSpeak.pdf>
- Cai, S., Venugopalan, S., Tomanek, K., Narayanan, A., Morris, M. R., & Brenner, M. P. (2022). *Context-Aware Abbreviation Expansion Using Large Language Models*. Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.91>
- Radford, A., Kim, J., Xu, T., Brockman, G., McLeavey, C., & Sutskever, I. (2023). *Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision*. <https://cdn.openai.com/papers/whisper.pdf>